

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON THE PERCEPTIONS OF AUDITORS AND ACCOUNTANTS (CAS) ON THE LEVEL OF ACCEPTANCE AND ADHERENCE TO SELECTED INDIAN ACCOUNTING STANDARDS ISSUED BY THE ICAI

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ABSTRACT

Debate over 'peer review' versus 'independent review' has been reignited since India established the National Financial Reporting Authority (NFRA) as an independent authority to audit the auditors. When it comes to appointing a regulator to oversee auditors on a worldwide scale, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI) is opposed to the proposal by the Indian government. This article investigates the views of auditors and other stakeholders in India on the auditing procedure. Financial reporting and accounting are still the primary means of communicating with investors and other stakeholders of a company. It's the language used in this kind of communication that's important. "Accounting standards are the syntax of the language used in such communication by entities." The increased complexity of today's firms, along with the separation of ownership and management that has resulted, has made prompt and accurate communication even more critical. Chartered Accountants (CAs) and practising auditors are surveyed in this research to get an understanding of their views on ICAI's professional code of conduct and Indian accounting standards. It is based on the results of a survey of competent accountants.

Keywords: Accounting Standards; Auditor's Perception; Code of Conduct; Ethical Code; Professional and Practicing Accountants.

I. INTRODUCTION

Only peer review has been used to control accountants in India for the last 16 years. Audit services in India are subject to restricted assessments by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), a professional accounting organisation. It was formed in 2002 by the ICAI's Peer Review Board to guarantee that the appropriate technical, professional, and ethical standards are adhered to in the performance of assurance service assignments. As an educational tool to improve the quality of professional work and openness in audit standards, peer review has no relation to any disciplinary or other regulatory system. In contrast to the SEC Practice Section (SECPS) of AICPA's AICPA Peer Review Program in the US, which performed 4,021 peer reviews and imposed 769 remedial measures over the period from 1977 to 1997, the Peer Review Board in India has relatively minimal relevance.

Its scope is restricted to the organisation of training programmes for reviewers and the issuance of Peer Review Certificates to businesses that have been examined.

To improve audit quality while retaining a self-regulation mechanism by the professional body of auditors, "the Indian government established the National Financial Reporting Authority (NFRA) in the wake of a heated debate over how to regulate public accountants in the wake of the over \$ 2 billion Punjab National Bank robbery." Indian Companies Act, 2013 Section 132(2) mandates that the National Financial Reporting Authority (NFRA) suggest to the government how accounting and auditing rules and standards should be formulated. To ensure that accounting and auditing standards are met, NFRA will monitor the quality of service provided by the various professionals involved and recommend methods to enhance service. This body has the investigative and judicial powers of an ordinary civil court, including the ability to punish and prohibit a public accountant or business from practising chartered accounting.

The ICAI will continue to play a regulatory function for its members in general and for audits of private and public unlisted firms below the threshold limit in particular.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Daugherty and Tervo (2010) Findings were made on the basis of replies from 146 accountants from small registered public accounting companies. PCAOB's early inspections seem to have a negative effect on smaller CPA firms, but medium and large CPA companies report good outcomes. Gramling et al (2011) found that PCAOB inspections had a corrective impact on minor auditors, and this is supported by Gramling et al (2011). DeFond and Lennox (2011) found that the fear of PCAOB inspections caused almost half of all small companies to quit their audit services. Large auditors may benefit from PCAOB inspections, but the data to support this claim is thin.

Dr. R. Anbalagan (2013) Of course, there's the widespread use of IFRS. The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have been in use in several countries for some time, and more are expected to join the movement in 2011. Korea, India, Japan, South and Central America, and Canada make up the next wave of changing nations. The United States is the most important nation in this way, but it's also the most mysterious. There is currently no decision on whether the United States would adopt International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). Despite this, the adoption date is currently more often stated as 2016 than 2014. An empirical examination of auditors' perceptions and the convergence of accounting standards to IFRS has been carried out in this research. "Global financial reporting has seen considerable transformations in the last several years." Convergence with IFRS is highly suggested in light of the current global economy and India's current situation. However, the move to IFRS will not be quick or painless, as might be asserted in the same breath. To implement the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), one would need to modify the style of accounts, implement new accounting standards, and demand more elaborate disclosures.

Ragothaman (2012) In her research, she contrasted the results of peer evaluations with those of PCAOB inspections and came to the conclusion that the latter were more thorough. In their 2013 study, Houston and Stefaniak looked at how partners at big, yearly-inspected audit firms saw themselves. When it came to auditing methods, they found that PCAOB inspectors were much less knowledgeable than Internal Quality Reviews.

A paper by **Gipper et al. (2015)** PCAOB audit inspections have a significant impact on investors' perceptions of reporting veracity. Financial reporting is more credible when audited by an independent body, according to this study..

Dr. Dhiraj Jain (2018) Accounting and auditing's corporate governance function has expanded substantially during the last two decades. Board and audit committee problems dominate discussions about corporate governance. For the time being, however, the findings of this study are limited to the consequences for Indian corporate governance and auditing. An audit committee is a crucial instrument for implementing corporate governance (CG) and ensuring its effectiveness and effectiveness (AC). An AC, which is required by SEBI clause 49 of the listing agreement, may greatly assist the board in developing, monitoring, and maintaining 'excellent' CG practises for the benefit of the company and all of its stakeholders. As several CG improvement measures were implemented during this period, the analysis is focused on this time period. We learn more about the function and duties of the audit committee by studying the audit, internal control, and financial reporting processes it oversees. Having a competent audit committee with an effective internal and external auditor in place would likely improve company performance and accountability, as the literature on the topic typically recommends.

Nandita Mishra, Mohamed Nurullah and Adel Sarea (2021) Since its inception in 2003, the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) has been working to improve the 2013 IR framework. A new version is expected in 2020. After a decade of progress, the authors know very little about how IR is seen by accountants and bookkeepers. The purpose of this article is to get an understanding of the present state of the adoption of IR in India by examining the views of the preparers. "It was determined that the top 500 firms on the ET 500 list were the ones under consideration." The survey did not include any banks or financial institutions (a total of 69). The questionnaire-based study assessed the state of IR in 431 organisations. Principle component analysis, a dimensionality reduction approach, was used to identify the most essential factors that influence a company's reputation. A case study technique has also been used to compare and evaluate IR trends in the manufacturing and industrial sectors. An overwhelming majority of businesses have a favourable view of IR, with the three most important factors influencing this view being clear reporting, efficient communication and more informed decision-making.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this Research Study is to analyze the perceptions of auditors and accountants (CAs) on the level of acceptance and adherence to selected Indian accounting standards issued by the ICAI.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The quality of data is inextricably tied to the method and technique used for collection. Hence, survey method through structured questionnaire was adopted for this study, as it was found to be suitable for this research.

Questionnaire design: - Samples of Chartered Accountants who were either practising CAs (Auditors) or Professional CA's were given questionnaires for the survey of Auditors and Accountants (Professional accountants). It took around eleven months to distribute the questionnaires and gather the data from the participants, which resulted in a sample size of 307 people. Five scales covering significant variables in accounting standards are utilised to gather data, and these 27 dimensions are reflected by chosen Indian accounting standards and covered in 87 items on the questionnaire.

Sampling frame: - To gather the primary data, questionnaires were sent to practising auditors and certified public accountants (CPA). "They represented a broad range of accounting businesses and corporations, the most of which were based in Tamil Nadu, India." The sample includes auditors who are either sole proprietors or partners in CPA companies, as well as CPAs at all levels of management, including junior, middle, and senior positions. 'Purposive Judgment sampling' was chosen since auditors and professional accountants are easily accessible for data collecting.

V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Analysis of the demographics and profession-related features of practising and professional CAs. The sample's demographics and career indicate a few noteworthy traits, which may be summed up as follows:

Table 1: Table Showing the Demographic Profiles of Respondents

Particulars	F	%
GENDER		
Female	45	14.7
Male	262	85.3
Total	307	100
AGE		
30 to 40 years	80	26.1
Below 30 years	14	4.6
Above 50 years	126	41.0
40 to 50 years	87	28.3
Total	307	100
SPECIALIZATION IN AUDITING		
Corporate Audit	48	15.6
Tax Audit	80	26.1

Any other Audit	9	2.9
Revenue Audit	19	6.2
All the above	151	49.2
Total	307	100
NO. OF YEARS EXPERIENCE IN THE FIELD		
5 years to 10 years	77	25.1
Less than 5 years	6	2.0
Above 15 years	168	54.7
10 years to 15 years	56	18.2
Total	307	100
AVERAGE ANNUAL INCOME		
5 lacs to 10 lacs	102	33.2
Less than 5 lacs	39	12.7
Above 20 lacs	81	26.4
10 lacs to 20 lacs	85	27.7
Total	307	100
TYPE OF ORGANISATIONS-PROFESSIONAL CAs EMPLOYED		
Government /Public Sector	10	6.2
Private Sector (India)	103	58.8
Private Sector (Multinational)	62	35.0
Total	175	100
RESPONDENTS CATEGORISATION		
Practicing Chartered accountants	132	43.0
Professional Chartered accountants	175	57.0
Total	307	100
STRUCTURE OF CLIENT FIRM OF PRACTISING CAs		
Partnership	66	50.0
Joint stock company	3	2.3
Individual	36	27.2
All the above	27	20.5
Total	132	100
FUNCTIONAL AFFILIATION OF PROFESSIONAL CAs		
Finance Dept	55	31.3
Accounts Dept	22	12.5
Corporate	18	10.2
Costing	10	5.7
Any other	9	5.1
All the above	61	35.2
Total	175	100

NATURE OF CLIENT BUSINESS OF PRACTISING CAs		
Manufacturing	13	9.8
Service Industry	5	3.8
Trading	23	17.5
All the above	91	68.9
Total	132	100

Important demographic characteristics are presented below, based on the sample survey of professional and practicing CAs as shown in the above table.

- ✚ Gender: 85.3% of all CAs are males and 14.7% of all CAs are females.
- ✚ Age group: 59% of the CAs are less than or equal to 50 years of age.
- ✚ Field of specialization: 49.2% have specialized in all three major types of audits namely Tax audit, corporate audit and Revenue audit.
- ✚ Marital status: 95.4% (293) of the respondent CAs are married
- ✚ Annual Income: 73.6% have an average annual income below Rs.20 lakhs.
- ✚ Years of Experience: 72.9% have an experience of over 10 years in the field.
- ✚ Organization Employment: 93.8% of the Professional CA respondents are employed in Private sector Organizations.
- ✚ Categorization of CAs: Professional CAs and Practicing CAs 43%.
- ✚ Nature of client business: Of the practicing CAs' 17.4% have clients of trading, 9.8% have clients of manufacturing, 3.8% have clients of service industry and 67.4% have clients in all three types of businesses.
- ✚ Client Organization structure: Of the practicing CAs' 27.3% have clients' as sole proprietors, 50% have clients' firm -partnership and 2.3% have clients of joint stock company and 20.5% have clients in all three forms.
- ✚ Functional affiliation: 35.2% of the Professional CAs have functional affiliation to all four major functions of accounts, finance, costing and corporate affairs.

Classification based on mean score for respondent perceptions of accounting standards.

Table 2: Showing the Perceptions of Accounting Standards Based on Mean Score

Accounting Standard	Description	Mean	Rank	Remarks
AS-11	Effects of changes in Foreign Exchange Rates	59.2157	27	BA
AS-20	Computation of Earnings per share	59.9131	26	BA
AS-14	Accounting for amalgamations	60.76	25	BA
AS-23	Accounting for investment in associate Co's.	61.3518	24	BA
AS-5	Prior period items & change in accounting policies	61.987	23	BA
AS-22	Accounting for taxes on income	62.1716	22	BA
AS-30	Accounting for Financial Instruments	63.3388	21	BA
AS-7	Construction contract accounting	63.6048	20	BA
AS-4	Contingencies & post balance sheet events	63.8654	19	BA
AS-24	Discontinuing Operations	64.582	18	BA
AS-25	Interim Financial Reporting	65.8198	17	BA
AS-16	Accounting for Borrowing costs	66.1455	16	AA
AS-21	Consolidated Financial Statements	66.4061	15	AA
AS-9	Revenue Recognition in the books	66.645	14	AA
AS-19	Accounting for Leases	66.7752	13	AA
AS-15	Accounting for employee benefits	66.8621	12	AA
AS-12	Accounting for Govt. Grants	67.2964	11	AA
AS-1	Disclosure of accounting policies	67.5733	10	AA
AS-18	Related party disclosures	67.7307	9	AA
AS-17	Segment reporting	68.4256	8	AA
AS-29	Accounting. for Provisions, Contingent Liabilities & assets	68.8599	7	AA
AS-13	Accounting for Investments	69.0771	6	AA
AS-27	Financial Reporting of Interest in JVs	69.1422	5	AA
AS-2	Valuation of Inventories	70.5972	4	AA
AS-3	Cash flow statements	71.4007	3	AA
AS-28	Impairment of Assets	71.4658	2	AA
AS-26	Intangible assets Reporting	73.6482	1	AA

AA: Above average; BA: Below average

The ranking of accounting standards on the basis of mean-score values indicates the following results: -

- ✚ The ranking of accounting standards on the basis of the value of mean score indicate the following top-5 ranked accounting standards':

Accounting standards	mean score
AS-28 (Impairment of assets)	71.466
AS-26 (Intangible assets)	73.648
AS-27(Financial Reporting of Interest in JVs)	69.142
AS-2(Valuation of inventory)	70.597
AS-28 (Impairment of assets)	71.466

The respondents high mean-value score for the above standards indicate that are presumed to be the most remembered and used accounting standards by the CAs in their professional career.

- ✚ The mean-score number is an average of 66.098. All 27 criteria were taken into consideration for the research, and of those 27 standards, 16 of them had a mean score above the average average, while 11 of them had an average score lower than that.
- ✚ Accounting standards with low mean-score values include, for example, the ones listed below.

Accounting standards	mean score
AS-20 (Computation of EPS)	59.913
AS-11 (Effects of changes in F/Exch. rates)	59.215
AS-5 (Prior period items/change in a/c policies)	61.351
AS-23 (Accounting for investment in associate Co's.)	61.351
AS-14 (Accounting for amalgamation)	60.760

They are assumed to be the least remembered and often utilised accounting standards by the CAs throughout their professional careers, based on the respondents' mean-value scores.

Analysis of perception on accounting standards based on demographic variables

The CAs' judgments of accounting standards are likely to be influenced by their personal traits. As a result, the variations in accounting standards amongst CAs are investigated using ANOVA (F test) on the basis of demographic data. Following are the findings and their relevance.

Table 3: Analysis of Perception on Accounting Standards Based on Demographic Variables

Variable	Mean Value	F-Value	P-Value	Level of Significance
Gender	65.13	1.072	.301	Not-Significant
Age	65.01	3.629	.000**	Significant
Years of experience	66.00	3.050	.000**	Significant
Field of specialization in Auditing	66.15	1.969	.000**	Significant
Nature of work	65.81	.307	.580	Not-Significant
Annual Income	65.46	2.318	.000**	Significant
Functional affiliation	66.17	1.523	.025*	Significant
CAs' employment Organization type	68.39	1.777	.004**	Significant
Type of client business	67.44	3.315	.000**	Significant
Type of client organization	65.36	1.734	.014*	Significant

Source: Primary data ** Highly Significant at 1% Level. * Significant at 5% Level.

- ✚ Accounting standards are highly regarded by both male and female CAs, and there is no substantial difference in their views based on gender.
- ✚ As people become older, their judgments of accounting standards rise dramatically among accountants.
- ✚ Grouped and studied on the basis of auditing speciality, CAs demonstrate a high level and reveals dramatically varied opinions towards accounting standards.
- ✚ Single and married Certified Public Accountants (CPAs) have similar views on accounting standards, and there was no substantial difference between the two groups. However, since they are younger, respondents who identify as single have a little higher mean value in their opinion than married respondents because they are more familiar with accounting standards revisions.
- ✚ The results suggest that as one's income rises, so does one's knowledge of and understanding of accounting rules.
- ✚ More experienced CAs have considerably different views on accounting standards than those with fewer than 10 years of experience, and this difference is much more pronounced for those with less than 10 years of experience.
- ✚ Public sector organisations using CAs have a higher degree of awareness about accounting standards than other organisations employing professional CAs in general. This is a major difference.
- ✚ Compared to the group of Practicing CAs, Professional CAs have a higher degree of perspective on accounting standards, and both groups exhibit no significant differences in perceptions of accounting standards.

- ✚ Compared to the group of Practicing CAs, Professional CAs have a higher degree of perspective on accounting standards, and both groups exhibit no significant differences in perceptions of accounting standards.
- ✚ CAs working for clients in the commerce and service industries are more likely to conform to accounting standards than those working for manufacturing companies. In addition, the attitudes of accounting standards among Professional CAs fluctuate greatly depending on the company sector they work in. In contrast to CPAs who are affiliated with only one type of client organisation structure, those who are affiliated with all four types of client organisation structures have significantly different perspectives on accounting standards and adhere to and follow them more closely than do CPAs affiliated only with sole proprietorships.
- ✚ According to CAs' functional affiliation, those who are affiliated to the function of corporate-accounts and accounts in general exhibit a high level of accounting standards perception and those who are affiliated to all functions like finance/accounts/corporate accounts generally exhibit lower accounting standards perception than those who are affiliated to any one of the functions. In addition, there are considerable differences in the attitudes toward accounting standards among CAs who are categorised according to their functional affiliation within the company in which they work.

VI. CONCLUSION

Different tactics must be developed by ICAI in order to meet the goals of member CAs in terms of 'accounting rules and standards,' as well as compliance with the 'professional code of conduct.' Creating a positive work environment for both professional and practising CPAs and recognising their functional, emotional, and managerial competency problems, as well as providing them with better platforms to voice their concerns and grievances, will help them maintain their belief in and commitment to better adherence to accounting standards and ensure that they continue to do so. For this purpose, more innovative programs are to be implemented by ICAI like: -

- ✚ Accountants and accounting officers in corporate entities, as well as practising auditors, should adhere to the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in the reporting structure to reduce industry failure symptoms, and ICAI should set up ethics departments to ensure that activities adhere to the codes of ethics, including the financial reporting process.
- ✚ Transparency in corporate governance made possible by technology
- ✚ Systematic problem solving techniques, case study analysis and exposure to modern auditing practises will help member CAs develop more ethical client relationships in well-conducted training workshops and seminars on Systematic problem solving techniques, case study analysis, and exposure to modern auditing practises.

CAs' judgments of accounting standards and professional ethics are not separate, but rather intertwined. This is the conclusion of this study. "As a result, both the workplace and

professional dedication are influenced by elements such as work values and how management employees see their own work experiences." According to the findings, an organization's degree of adherence to accounting standards and adherence to professional codes of ethical behaviour is influenced by factors such as the work environment, professional work values, and opportunities for professional excellence. Accountants need ethical norms to provide accurate financial reports devoid of major misstatements, the researchers found after their investigation.

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